

A REVIEW ON THE EFFICACY OF SHUNTHYADI TAIL NASYA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF VATAJA PRATISHAYA

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ABSTRACT

Pratishayaya one of the Nasaroga is explained by acharyas in detail in all classical books. It is considered as the most important disease as, if it is neglected or not treated properly leads to complication such as diseases of ear, throat, head. So it must be treated in time with proper medicines. Nasya is one of important panchkaram helps, For Remove obstruction of urdhva-Jatrugata doshas nasya is the superior therapy that's why for this study we use nasya karma for management of vataj pratishyaya, Shunthyadi tail is used for nasya mentioned in sushrut samhita. for this study 15 were studied.

KEYWORDS: Pratisyaya, vataj pratishyaya, Shunthyadi tail, Nasya karma, Urdhvajatrugata roga.

INTRODUCTION

Pratishyaya is one of the important Nasaroga. Pratishyaya has been a major problem for physicians for a long time. Vata is the main dosha and kaph, pitta, rakta are associated dosha. This pathogenesis occurs when a causative factor specifically vitiates vata causing vatavridhi. Kapha, Pitta and Rakta are in sama avastha and they obstruct the gati of Vata. These Doshas get lodged in Shira Pradesha and the Vridhavastha starts expelling kapha, pitta and rakta through the nose causing Pratishaya. Pratishaya one of the nasaroga is explained by acharyas in detail in all classical books .It is considered as the most important disease as, if it is neglected or not treated properly leads to complication such as diseases of ear, throat, head. So it must be treated in time with proper medicines.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To study the efficacy of Sunthyadi tail Nasya in the management of Pratishyaya.

To review the procedure of Nasyakarama in detail.

To study the etiology, pathology and clinical features of Vataj pratishaya in ayurvedic and modern science.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of patients

Patients Randomly selected from OPD and IPD of dept. of shalakyatantra of S.S.T's AYURVED MEDICAL COLLEGE. While showing signs and symptoms of Vataj Pratishaya, they were selected for the study. Total number of 15 patients were registered A regular record of the assessment of all patients was maintained according to Performa prepared for the purpose.

Inclusion criteria

Patient willing to participate in the trial

Patients between 20 to 50 years of age

Patients presenting with signs and symptoms of Vataj Pratishyaya mentioned in Ayurvedic classics and rhinitis according to modern texts.

Nasya Yogya Patients.

Exclusion criteria

1. Patients below the age of 20 years and above 50 years
2. Patients not willing for trial
3. Those having history of Hypertension and Diabetes mellitus or associated with obesity.
4. Those with any chronic debilitating infectious disease.
5. Those with any inflammatory disease and those requiring surgical treatment

Subjective parameters

1. Nasastrav
2. Nasaavrodh,
3. kshavthu,
4. Galashushkta,
5. Shirashool

Objective parameters

Absolute eosinophilic count, nasal smear test if Required.

Selection of drugs

Sunthyadi Tail were prepared in our rasashastra dept. all Churna were purchased from GMP approved pharmacy. Analysis for chemical properties were done from an analytical lab.

Dose

Sunthyadi Tail 6 drops in each Nostril

Nasya karma is carried out for 7 days.

Follow up – 1st Day, 7th Day, 15th Day.

Nasya chikitsa

Administration of medicine through the nose is called Nasya.

I. Purva karma - snehan with til tail and tap swed with warm water.

II. Pradhan Karma - Shunthyadi tail used for Nasya. Dose- 6 drops in each nostril for 7 days

III. Pashchat karma – kaval with kosha jal.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

This is a randomized clinical trial carried out on 15 diagnosed patients of Vataj pratishyay. There were 15 patients selected as per Aim; Exclusion AND Inclusion criteria. For data Analysis paired t test were used AND Result were follows

Symptoms	No. of Pt	BT	AT	%	SD	SE	T Value	P Value
Nasastrava	9	2.87	0.67	78.3	1.19	0.48	7.58	<0.0001
Nasaavrodh	13	2.31	0.38	73	0.23	0.31	8.18	<0.0001
kshavthu	10	2.65	0.55	62.3	0.31	0.30	6.00	<0.0001
Galashushkta	12	1.92	0.47	65.6	0.37	0.50	7.15	<0.0001
Shirashool	14	2.53	0.49	75.3	0.31	0.35	9.5	<0.0001

DISCUSSION

Nasya Karma had a major role in the management of all Urdhva Jathurgata Rogas. Recurrence of the disease occurs because the Doshas have not been evacuated completely. Such Doshas reside in their latent stage (predisposing stage) & give rise to the same disease when factors (aggravating factors) are favourable. Description of Allergy & allergic disorders can be seen in Brihatrayi under heading of Ritu Sandhi, Virudha Ahara & Dushivisha

all of them are the results of an Asatmyaja Vyadhi. Suthyadi tail not only expel out the doshas also helps to increase the power of deepan pachan, so It shows tremendous results in the management of Pratishyaya.

CONCLUSION

Sunthyadi Tail is effective in the management of Vataj Pratishya.

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